

MODAL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE PLATE BY USING ANSYS**A.Lakshmaiah, B.Thimothi¹, S.B.K.Reddy, M.D.V.Vara Prasad, Dr L.Ramesh^{1*}**

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Abstract

This study thoroughly investigates the vibration responses of fibre-reinforced laminated composite plates, focusing on identifying mode shapes and calculating natural frequencies. Theoretical calculations, based on the material properties, geometric dimensions, and boundary conditions, were performed to determine the natural frequencies at which the plate vibrates naturally under dynamic loads. A comprehensive modal analysis using ANSYS software involved creating a detailed 3D model of the composite plate with ply orientations set at 0 degrees and 90 degrees to study the effects of fibre orientation on the plate's vibration characteristics. Mode shapes, representing specific deformation patterns at each natural frequency, were identified, providing critical insights into the movement of different parts of the plate during vibration. The comparison of theoretical natural frequencies with those derived from ANSYS simulations showed a strong correlation, validating the accuracy of both the theoretical models and the ANSYS simulations. The results highlighted the natural frequencies for specific modes (Mode 11, Mode 21, and Mode 22), showing close agreement between theoretical and analytical values. This study demonstrates that theoretical models can accurately predict the natural frequencies and mode shapes of fibre-reinforced laminated composite plates. The close match between theoretical and analytical results underscores the reliability of ANSYS software for conducting modal analysis in composite materials. Identifying mode shapes and natural frequencies is crucial for designing and optimizing composite structures to withstand operational loads and dynamic forces without experiencing excessive vibrations or failures.

Keywords: Composite Materials, Modal Analysis, ANSYS, Natural Frequencies, Fibre Reinforced Composite.

1. Introduction

Nature utilizes optimized reinforcing fiber orientation to develop plant structures capable of withstanding natural forces like wind-induced bending. This concept inspired the design of similar man-made composites, leading to systematic experimental investigations into the effects of fiber orientation. Composite materials consist of two or more constituent materials with distinct physical or chemical properties. When combined, these materials create a composite with properties that differ from those of its individual components. The components retain their separate identities within the final structure. Composite materials are valued for various reasons, including their enhanced strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and high tensile strength and modulus (Ahmed et al., 2015). These qualities make composites a crucial and practical alternative for numerous applications requiring specific mechanical behaviors. Natural frequency, also known as Eigen frequency, refers to the frequency at which a system naturally oscillates in the absence of external driving or damping forces. The oscillation pattern exhibited by a system at its natural frequency is termed its normal mode, where all parts of the system move sinusoidally at that particular frequency.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The literature reviewed encompasses a range of studies utilizing diverse analytical approaches to investigate the natural frequencies and vibration characteristics of composite plates. Pushparaj Pingulkar et al. conducted numerical simulations using ANSYS to ascertain the natural frequencies and mode shapes of cantilevered glass fiber reinforced polymer composites (GFRPCs) and carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRPCs). They analyzed laminates comprising 8 ply cantilevered plates with varying fiber volume fractions (0.3, 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6), and validated their ANSYS results against existing literature, demonstrating strong agreement [1]. Farzad Ebrahimi et al. presented analytical solutions for the natural vibration of composite plates made from multi-scale hybrid nano composites. Their study focused on epoxy matrix reinforced with carbon fiber (CF) and carbon nano tube (CNT), employing graphical illustrations to elucidate how different parameters impact vibration responses [2]. Arvind K. Singh et al. explored composite materials as lightweight, high-strength alternatives to metals in aerospace applications. Using finite element analysis based on first-order shear deformation theory, they investigated the free vibration characteristics of laminated composite plates. They found that vibration frequencies were influenced by variables such as width-to-thickness ratio, fiber orientation, and plate edge conditions [3]. B. Sidda Reddy et al. utilized D-optimal designs

and response surface methodology to predict natural frequencies of clamped laminated composite plates. Their study employed carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) with various fiber orientations (-45° , 0° , 45° , and 90°), analyzing how these orientations affected vibration behavior [4]. W. A. Benfield et al. proposed a method to determine vibration modes of complex structural systems by synthesizing component vibration modes. They emphasized the application of their method in enhancing the performance and operation of aircraft wing structures [5]. Vinayak Kallannavar et al. highlighted the widespread use of laminated composite and sandwich structures in industrial applications due to their favorable physical and mechanical properties. They discussed these structures as "smart structures," capable of adapting to diverse functionalities [6]. Dr. Joseph Michael Mahoney et al. described a mechanical vibrations course focused on theoretical and simulation-based learning, acknowledging the challenges of limited hands-on experience with physical components [7]. Srividhya et al. defined vibrations as periodic motions induced by external forces in rigid or elastic bodies, classifying them into harmonic and random types [8]. Trung-Kien Nguyen et al. presented static and vibration analyses of isotropic and functionally graded sandwich plates using higher-order shear deformation theory. Their numerical examples involved Al/ZrO₂ and Al/Al₂O₃ plates under simply supported and clamped boundary conditions, demonstrating the validity and accuracy of their analytical approaches. Overall, these studies collectively contribute to advancing the understanding and application of composite materials and structural dynamics through sophisticated analytical methodologies in engineering fields.

3. Designing of Composite Plate

A composite material (also called a composition material or shortened to composite, which is the common name) is a material which is produced from two or more constituent materials.[1] These constituent materials have notably dissimilar chemical or physical properties and are merged to create a material with properties unlike the individual elements. There are various reasons where new material can be favoured. Typical examples include materials which are less expensive, lighter, stronger or more durable when compared with common materials.

3.1 Modelling of composite plate

For simulation 3D model should be designed. So by using the dimensions model is designed in ANSYS software.

PARAMETER	DATA
Length of FRC	2m
Width of composite plate	1m
Ply Thickness of FRC	0.0025m
Composite plate thickness	0.1m
Ply orientation angle	0,90,90,0

Table 1: Modelling details of composite plate

Fig 1: Meshing of component

Fig 2: Fiber orientation at 0°

Fig 3: Fiber orientation at 90°

Composite material is modelled in ANSYS software. This model used in ANSYS to compare the theoretical values with the analytical values. And observed the mode shapes with this model analysis. Analysis of composite plate is carried out by following ones.

- ✓ Composite plate ply orientation at 0 angle
- ✓ Composite plate ply orientation at 90 angle
- ✓ Composite plate ply orientation at 90 angle
- ✓ Composite plate ply orientation at 0 angle

And theoretical and analytical values are compare at modes as.

- ✓ Mode (1,1)
- ✓ Mode (2,1)
- ✓ Mode (2,2)

4. Results and discussions

4.1 Theoretical Calculations

Formula of Natural Frequency For All Edges Are Simply Supported Laminated Composite Plate

$$\omega_{mn} = \frac{\pi^2}{\sqrt{\rho_m h}} \left[D_1 \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^4 + 2D_3 \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^2 \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^2 + D_2 \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^4 \right]^{1/2}$$

To Convert the Unit into Hertz,

$$f_{mn} = \frac{\omega_{mn}}{2\pi} \text{ Natural Frequency of Vibration in Cycles per Second (Hertz)}$$

D= Flexural Stiffness

ρ_m = Density

A = Length Long Edge

B= Length of Short Edge

M = Half Wave Number Of Long Edge

N = Half Wave Number of Short Edge

ω_n = Natural Circular Frequency In Radians Per Unit Time

4.2 Analytical Results

Fig 4: Composite plate mode shape with 15.684 Hz.

Fig 5: Composite plate mode shape with 29.357 Hz.

Fig 6: Composite plate mode shape with 52.128 Hz0

Fig 7: Composite plate mode shape with 54.834 Hz.

Fig 8: Composite plate mode shape with 63.135 Hz.

Fig 9: Composite plate mode shape with 83.73 Hz.

4.3 Result Table

S.NO	Mode	Natural frequency (Hz), theoretical.	Natural frequency (Hz), analytical.
1	(1,1)	15.69	15.684

2	(2,1)	29.38	29.31
3	(2,2)	62.75	62.694

Table 2: Theoretical and analytical Natural frequency of composite plate

CONCLUSION

This study thoroughly investigated the vibration responses of fiber-reinforced laminated composite plates, focusing on identifying mode shapes and calculating natural frequencies. Theoretical calculations were performed based on the material properties, geometric dimensions, and boundary conditions to determine the natural frequencies, representing the specific frequencies at which the plate vibrates naturally under dynamic loads. A comprehensive modal analysis using ANSYS software involved creating a detailed 3D model of the composite plate with ply orientations set at 0 degrees and 90 degrees. This helped study the effects of fiber orientation on the plate's vibration characteristics. Mode shapes, or specific deformation patterns at each natural frequency, were identified, providing insights into the movement of different parts of the plate during vibration, essential for designing structures to withstand dynamic loads.

The theoretical natural frequencies were compared with those derived from ANSYS simulations, showing a strong correlation. This validated the accuracy of both the theoretical models and the ANSYS simulations in predicting the composite plate's vibration behavior. The results table highlighted the natural frequencies for specific modes (Mode 11, Mode 21, and Mode 22), showing close agreement between theoretical and analytical values. For example, Mode 11 had a natural frequency of 15.69 Hz theoretically and 15.684 Hz analytically.

- Theoretical models accurately predicted the natural frequencies and mode shapes of fiber-reinforced laminated composite plates.
- The close match between theoretical and analytical results validated the reliability of ANSYS software for modal analysis in composite materials.

- Identifying mode shapes and natural frequencies is crucial for designing and optimizing composite structures to withstand operational loads and dynamic forces without excessive vibrations or failures.

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